

Energy Policy Monitor

OPEN INSIGHTS

**Conservative Party of Canada
Federal Election Platform 2021**

May 2026

For the EPM team

The following deck is a mock-up of what this could look like at release.

We plan to consult with a communications expert regarding what's best in terms of the format and content for EPM, considering our audience and the analysis in question.

About the Assessment

This document summarizes the results of our assessment of the Conservative Party of Canada's 2021 federal election platform. We compare the platform's stated energy and climate policies against a current-policies baseline (the 'reference scenario') to estimate their impact on Canada's greenhouse gas emissions, energy system, and technology deployment pathways.

This assessment does not interpret the platform for policy implications. It presents modelling methods and outputs transparently. Our full input dataset including policy assumptions are publicly available, along with model code.

Policies Repealed	Policies Introduced
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Federal consumer fuel levy (a.k.a. the carbon tax)● Federal Clean Fuel Regulations	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● 30% ZEV mandate for light-duty vehicles by 2030● 15% Renewable Natural gas mandate● \$5 B in Carbon Capture Tax Credit● Low Carbon Fuel Standard - 20% reduction in carbon intensity of transport fuels by 2030● Personal low carbon saving account (\$50/tonne by 2030)

Key Findings

Proposed policies modestly reduce emissions. However, our analysis does not support the claim that Canada will be on track to our Paris climate commitments by 2030.

- We estimate that emissions will fall by 6% from current levels to 2030, versus the Paris target (35% decrease)
- By 2050, proposed policies reduce emissions by 50Mt CO₂e per year
- Emissions reductions in oil and gas and transport are partly offset by increases in industry and electricity generation
- The economy grows, on aggregate, but with sectoral winners and losers
- Demand for gasoline and diesel declines, while natural gas and clean fuels rise
- Electric vehicle adoption accelerates load growth, while natural gas and onshore wind compete for new electricity generation capacity

Proposed policies modestly reduce emissions

Emissions reductions in oil and gas and transport are partly offset by increases in industry and electricity generation

Conservative platform provides a modest GDP boost through 2035

National GDP, real (CAD billion)

+1.2%

Conservative vs. Reference in 2035

Both scenarios show sustained absolute GDP growth. Near-term macro impacts are modest — the Conservative platform stays slightly ahead throughout 2025–35.

While national GDP is similar between scenarios, provincial GDP diverges significantly in Alberta and Quebec

GDP % difference vs. Reference scenario

- Alberta**
2030: +6.0% 2035: +29.5%
Oil & gas and petroleum refining surge with CCS tax credit driving investment.
- Ontario**
2030: +7.2% 2035: +1.5%
Early gains in services and trade largely offset by motor vehicle manufacturing headwinds from ZEV-driven demand shifts.
- Quebec**
2030: -14.2% 2035: -20.7%
Higher electricity prices penalise electro-intensive industry. Limited fossil-fuel exposure.

Near-term sectoral shifts widen sharply by 2035

Sectoral output, difference from Reference scenario (%), 2030 and 2035

▼ Vehicles lose

ZEV mandate shifts auto demand toward imported EVs.

↔ Agriculture reverses sign

Initial input-cost savings from carbon tax removal reverse by 2035 as demand-side shifts and loss of rebate returns accumulate.

▲ Oil, gas & services win

Carbon tax removal lowers production costs. CCS tax credit drives investment.

Electric vehicle adoption accelerates load growth

National electricity demand, Petajoules

% of new light-duty vehicle sales

Natural gas and onshore wind compete for new electricity generation capacity

National electricity generation capacity additions, Gigawatts

In 2045, onshore wind makes up >50% of capacity additions, despite absence of strong low-carbon policy in the power sector

Demand for gasoline and diesel declines, while natural gas and clean fuels rise

Differences from reference scenario, Petajoules

EPM assessments do not endorse, recommend, or evaluate any policy platform.

This summary does not interpret or evaluate the platform. This assessment applies the same standardized methodology to all parties and platforms.

EPM presents model outputs transparently. Full data, code, and assumptions are publicly available.

About Energy Policy Monitor

The **Energy Policy Monitor delivers** independent, timely analysis of Canada's major energy and climate policy developments. Led by the [Open Insights](#) team, EPM cuts through complexity to provide clear, evidence-based assessments of what new policies mean for emissions trajectories, energy systems, and economic outcomes.

More information about the EPM and other assessments can be found at epm.openinsights.ca.